

8T – Spinning Curvature Vortexes and Interference

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July 3, 2021

Abstract:

By analyzing the new framework led by the coupling constants primordial equation, which proved bosons to be net curvature of discrete amounts, isomorphic to the prime numbers, it is than possible to construct and reason the physical phenomena of interference in a completely different way – based on spinning curvature vortexes.

Introduction

The new 8T framework regard fermions and in particular quarks as arbitrary variations of a manifold which vanish into matter. The process of vanishing ensuring that no curvature is allowed, as in equation (1.1).

$$\left[\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \right] \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \left[\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \right] \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} \delta g' = 0 \quad (1)$$

The proof of (1.1) to be fermions was by discretizing and partitioning the arbitrary variation term in (1.1), and by proving the series must have only two distinct elements that differ in sign and vanish to zero. By allowing the elements to vary, we proven they form eight threefold combinations.

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

Later in the 8T thesis, we proven the coupling constants series by making three theorems on the varying manifold. We proved the idea right by calculating the fine structure constants based on the value of the previous term, we did not use any pre-measured constant such as the speed of light or the Planck constant. The coupling series is isomorphic to prime numbers or one and associated with the term:

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0 \quad (1.2)$$

Bosons are ripples of discrete magnitude, which are curvature vortexes spinning on the matrix tensor.

$$8 + (1):(24 + (3)) + 3:(120 + (3)) + 5:(840 + (3)) + 7 \dots \quad (1.31)$$

For example, the photon is associated with discrete amount of curvature, generated by the invariant (3), and proved the electron. The overall representation gives us the propagation picture for the third coupling term:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.32)$$

Moreover, in spin representation:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N2 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2} \quad (1.33)$$

The visualization of the Boson in the theory:

Since it has spin, the net curvature is than a vortex of certain amount:

In addition, interference than could be constructed as two opposite curvature vortexes interfacing with one another. The area of cancelation is the area in which the opposite ripples on the matric tensor interest. The spinning curvature vortex is a more compete version of the phenomena of interference as it takes into account the two representations of the coupling constants series. The net curvature on the matric tensor given by equations (1.34-1.35) and the prime critical line, i.e. spin.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (1.34)$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30: 128: 850: 9254.. \quad (1.35)$$

So now, we can visualize the phenomena of interference in the following way by the two representations:

If we define ripple operators \varnothing from a starting area to another area, the mutual area of both will be the amount of interference.

$$\varnothing: A \rightarrow B \quad (1.4)$$

$$\varnothing: A' \rightarrow B \quad (1.41)$$

Interference will accrue at the manifold segment that is mutual to both starting point. Define the interference operator:

$$\approx: A \cap A' \quad (1.42)$$

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)
- [2] O. Manor. "The Coupling Constants Series Curvature Vortexes" In: (2021)